
An Appraisal of Security Requirements in the Law of Banking as the Last Resort that Banks Rely upon to Recover Loans Granted to their Defaulting Customers in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The Law of Banking refers to the body of Legal Rules and principles that regulate the governing of banking business importantly, the relationship between banker and their customers. It covers core banking activities such as the acceptance of deposits, operation of accounts, the granting of loan and advances. In contemporary commercial practice, banking institutions play a central role in stimulating economic growth through the provision of credit facilities such as loan, overdraft, advances and other forms of financial accommodation that enable individuals, corporate bodies and even governmental institutions to finance consumption, investment and expansion that strengthen modern commerce which otherwise would have been severely restricted. However, lending is inherently risky once money leaves the possession of the bank or lender, repayment depends largely on the borrower's willingness and ability to honour the agreed terms. Although every credit facilities are backed by a contractual obligation to repay either on demand or at specified time. Reality occurrence over time has demonstrated that defaulters are common in their defaulting habits. In Nigeria, our court system, have consistently upheld bank's right to demand repayments of sum advanced. Nevertheless, the enforcement of such repayment may become complicated where the borrower lacks the means or refuses to pay. It is in this context, that security becomes crucial though not the primary source of repayment but secondary. In the law of banking, security operates as the banker's ultimate safeguard and protective mechanism relied upon on defaults when all other means of recovery failed.

This appraisal critically examines and evaluates the legal framework underpinning operational modalities, judicial interpretations, concepts, elements, characteristics, types, enforcement and policy implications of security as the ultimate secondary loan recovery mechanism rooted from statute such as BOFIA Act 2020, CAMA 2020, NDIC, Case Law and CBN guidelines. It argues that while security boosts lender confidence, its relegation as last resort status exemplifies equitable lending practices in Nigeria's evolving credit landscape. The discourse is particularly pertinent amid Nigeria's 2025 Non-Performing Loan (NPL) ratio of 4.2% down to 5.2% in 2024 attributable to robust regulatory interventions emphasizing negotiation over enforcement.

KEYWORDS: Security, Loan, Overdraft, Advances, Repayment, Legal Frameworks and Last Resorts.

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INTRODUCTION

In modern day commerce and banking, credit facilities are very essential in facilitating economic growth, efficiency in both personal and business finance. Credit facilities are part of the financial services rendered by banks and other financial institutions to individuals, businesses, governmental institution designed to provide funds, overdraft and advances that can be obtained as needed often with agreed terms for repayment furnished with interest rates. Credit facilities allow businesses, individual and corporate bodies to manage their cash flow, provide means for expansion, invest in projects, make large purchases, even allow banks and other financial institutions to generate interest incomes, fees and charges. A loan is a type of credit facility where a lender provides a certain amount of fund to a borrower which must be repaid with interest over a fixed period of time. An overdraft on the

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other hand, is a credit facility that allows an honest and seasoned customer or borrower to withdraw more money from their account than the available balance.

One of the major risks inherent in the banker-customer relationship is the possibility that a customer may default in repaying loans granted by the bank. To manage this risk and ensure recovery, the law governing banking transactions permits bankers to demand and take security for protection of repayment from the customer. However, where a bank grants a credit facility like a loan or overdraft, there is an understanding whether express or implied that the bank has a right to repayment of such amount either on demand or upon expiration of a fixed date. In the case of *Angigu v. Malami*¹, the court held that where a bank grants an overdraft, demand for its repayment is expected to be done by the borrower after reasonable notice had been given. The relationship between a banker and customer is essentially contractual and has been judicially recognized as that of debtor and creditor as established in the case of *Forley v. Hill*², where the House of Lords held that money paid into a bank becomes the property of the bank and the bank's obligation is merely to repay an equivalent sum to the customer on demand. The relationship was also firmly established in the case of *Joachimson v. Swiss Bank Corporation*³, where the court held that banks act as debtors to their customers and must honour cheques provided that sufficient funds exist. This principle was complemented by *Tournies v. National Provincial and Union Bank of England*⁴, which defined the duty of confidentiality owed by banks to their clients, subject to exceptions such as legal compulsion or public interest. Nigerian jurisprudence further refined banking obligations, in the case of *ACB Ltd v. Babayemi*⁵, where the court clarified evidentiary requirements for providing debts arising from overdrafts, while the case of *ACB Ltd v. Oba*⁶, addressing the admissibility of bank statements under the Evidence Act setting conditions for the use of the court. Finally, the case of *United Bank for Africa (UBA) v. Ibhafidon*⁷ reinforced the principle that banks must prove indebtedness with proper documentation before recovering loans, underscoring the importance of accurate records in financial disputes.

However, the granting of credit facilities further exposes banks to the risk of default, for this reason, banks usually require security before advancing loans to customers. Security is regarded as the last resort of bankers because, the primary expectation is that the borrower will repay the facility from his income, salary or business profits. The bank does not ordinarily intend to realize the security, it is only when the customer either fails or refuses to repay the loan, that the bank falls back on the security as a means of recovering the outstanding debt. Thus, security becomes the banker's last resort on which it can rely to recover the amount due from his defaulting customers, such security, also becomes enforceable upon default. It is rooted in contract law, commercial law, statutory regulations and has been shaped significantly by judicial decisions. The law relating to security is very important in banking practice, having over time provided the legal framework through which banks can enforce their rights and recover loans granted to their defaulting customers. In purely economic and regulatory terms, the principle that security enforcement constitutes the last resort underscores a cardinal principle of banking law in respect of prioritization of amicable resolution over adversarial proceedings. This doctrine deeply embedded in Nigerian jurisprudence and regulatory frameworks, mandating banks to exhaust all non-confrontational recovery avenues before resorting to the safeguards of borrower's dignity and economic viability, that also aligns with the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) overreaching mandate to foster a stable financial system.

2. Concept Of Security In Banking Law

Security in law of banking refers to any form of assurance which secures a loan or advances made by banks to their customers. It is any proprietary interest or personal right taken by banks over a customer's property or against a third party to secure the repayment of a loan. It also gives the banks an assurance that the debt will be recovered if the customer defaults. Security is a legal interest in a property or assets that is granted to the lender of a loan by a borrower to secure the repayment of a debt or the performance of an obligation. Essentially, security acts as a collateral or form of assurance that the lender can claim if the borrower defaults. It is further a legal mechanism through which the bank acquires an enforceable right or interest in the borrower's asset, which can be realized if the borrower defaults in repayment. Security may take different forms, such as mortgage over land, charges over company assets, pledge of goods, lien or guarantee by a third party, however, regardless of its form, the essence of security is to provide the bank with an additional source of repayment apart from the personal promise of the borrower.

Further, the main reason why security is required in banking transactions is because, lending involves risk. When a bank grants a loan or overdraft, it's lending out money that belongs to depositors, there is always the possibility that the borrower may fail to repay, because of this risk, banks protect themselves by demanding security before granting credit facilities. In Nigeria, the

¹ *Angigu v. Malami (1992) 1 NWLR.*

² *Forley v. Hill (1848) 1 LR.*

³ *Joachimson v. Swiss Bank Corporation (1921) 1 ELR.*

⁴ *Tournies v. National Provincial and Union Bank of England (1924) 1 AELR.*

⁵ *ACB Ltd v. Babayemi (1969) 2 NBLR 231.*

⁶ *ACB Ltd v. Oba (1993) 7 NWLR (Pt. 304).*

⁷ *United Bank for Africa (UBA) v. Ibhafidon (1994) 1 NWLR (Pt. 318).*

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economy has experienced period of recession, inflation and foreign exchange instability, many businesses have collapsed or struggled due to high production cost, unstable electricity supply and changing government policies, in such a situation, borrower may genuinely be unable to repay loan. There are also cases where some borrowers divert loan funds to other purposes or mismanagement of loan money, all these factors increase the rate of loan defaults.

In the past, Nigeria banks has faced serious problem with non-performing loans which inversely affected the stability of the banking sector. This shows why security is not just a formality but a necessary precaution. It developed as a way of reducing losses and protecting the financial system from collapse. Therefore, the rationale behind security is to manage risk and ensure that banks have some form of assurances in case if repayment fails, the banks does not usually intend to seize or sell the borrower's property. Although, enforcing security can be stressful and time consuming, for instance, it involves legal procedure and compliance with statutory requirements, court processes can take time and selling of the secured property may not come easy, banks therefore, prefer voluntary repayment. It is only when the borrower defaults and all reasonable demands for repayment fails, that the bank enforces to take over the security in their custody and recover the outstanding debts, this is why it described as the banker's last line of defense. The requirement of security by banks to protect loan granted to their defaulting customers is also central to banking practice because it protects against credit risks. In *Swiss Bank Corporation v. Lloyds Bank Ltd*⁸, the House of Lords emphasized that security creates priority in favour of secured creditors over unsecured creditors, thereby, strengthening the banker's position upon default.

However, the requirements of security by banks requires certain essential elements to make it valid and enforceable. The borrower must have legal ownership or title over the asset being pledge and the security must be backed by proper documentation such as a mortgage deed or guarantee agreement. The asset should be marketable, meaning capable of being sold or realized if default occurs and its value must be adequate to cover the loan. The security must also comply with statutory requirements to ensure legality and in some cases, the bank must take possession or control assets to perfect its interest. A good security must also have the characteristic to be valid, sufficiency or adequate value to cover the bank entire exposure because of the downward fluctuations in value, it is necessary to leave sufficient margin between the value of the security and the bank's exposure. A good security must also be easily realizable without too much cost or delay in realization. A good security must be capable of being valued in a relatively objective rather than sentimental manner. A good security must have an unquestionable title, not onerous, not impose undue liabilities or inconveniences to the bank. A good security must be in prime location and borrower's prime assets among others.

In evaluating the credit worthiness of a bank customer before lending a specified amount of money since credit worthiness refers to the likelihood that a borrower will repay their debts in time. The banks must look into the following situation and considerations: capital as stake or interest in a business, capability of the borrower to generate income that ensuring repayment, the character of honesty and reliability of the borrower, the conditions or economic status and finally, the connection of other accounts which can be linked to the borrower in order to aid the bank in recovering his debt through means of set-off. In spite of the various condition of credit worthiness, it does not clearly guarantee that a borrower would repay his loan and this necessitated the need to request for security as a last resort through which the bank can get its loan recovered in the event of non-repayment.

3. TYPES OF SECURITY

Bank security may be broadly classified as personal or real securities. Personal security relies on credit worthiness of a third party rather than the property, while real security involve proprietary interest in the property/assets.

(i) Mortgage

A mortgage is the conveyance of an interest in property as security for the repayment of a debt or the performance of an obligation. The borrower is known as the mortgagor, while the lender is the mortgagee. Land is the most common and universally accepted form of banking security, and in law, land includes fixtures attached to it. A mortgage affecting land cannot be validly created without the consent of the Governor or Local Government Chairman, as applicable.

In the case of *Savannah Bank of Nigeria Ltd v Ajilo*⁹, a legal mortgage was created and registered to secure advances granted by the bank. When the customer defaulted, the bank sought to sell the property. However, the mortgage was created without the Governor's consent. The Supreme Court held that failure to obtain the required consent rendered the mortgage null and void. This position was reaffirmed in the case *Innih v Ferado A&C Ltd*¹⁰ and the case of *UBN v Ayo Dare & Sons (Nig.) Ltd*¹¹.

⁸*Swiss Bank Corporation V. Lloyds Bank Ltd (1979) 3 WLR 201.*

⁹*Savannah Bank of Nigeria Ltd v Ajilo (1989) 1 NWLR*

¹⁰*Innih v Ferado A&C Ltd (1990) 5NWLR (Pt. 152)*

¹¹*UBN v Ayo Dare & Sons (Nig.) Ltd (2000) II NWLR (Pt. 679)*

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There are two different types of mortgage and they are Equitable and Legal Mortgages:

Equitable Mortgage: An equitable mortgage may be created in three ways:

1. Deposit of title deeds without documentation, known as an informal mortgage, provided there is an implied agreement that the deposit is for security. In the case of *ACB v Nnaji*¹², the customer applied for an overdraft and a third party deposited his title deeds with the bank as guarantee, though no formal deed or memorandum was executed. The court held that since the bank granted the overdraft, the guarantee was valid and binding.
2. Deposit of title deeds with a memorandum of deposit. which evidences the transaction and its terms.
3. Deposit of title deeds with a memorandum of deposit and an irrevocable power of attorney, authorizing the bank to execute a legal mortgage if necessary. The power of attorney must be by deed and duly stamped.

Legal Mortgage: A legal mortgage is the safest form of mortgage for banks. It is created by executing a deed of mortgage which conveys the mortgagor's interest in the property to the bank, subject to redemption upon repayment. Banks usually use pre-printed mortgage deed forms signed by the customer.

A mortgagee has several remedies upon default and they include:

1. **Right of Possession:** The bank may take possession of the mortgaged property and appoint a manager or receiver to collect rents, particularly where the loan is small and rental income is viable.
2. **Right of Foreclosure:** Foreclosure extinguishes the mortgagor's right of redemption and vests ownership in the mortgagee. This right can only be exercised through a court order.
3. **Right of Sale:** The mortgagee's right of sale is statutory and does not need to be expressly stated in the mortgage deed (**Section 123, Property and Conveyancing Law 1959**).

Key rules governing sale include:

- The power of sale cannot be exercised where the amount owed is in dispute.
- The loan must be due and the mortgagor must be in default after notice.
- In the case of *Ojikutu v Agbonmagbe Bank Ltd*¹³, the bank issued notice and later suspended the sale upon promise of payment but sola without issuing a fresh notice after default. The court held that the original notice remained valid.
- In third-party mortgages, reasonable notice must be given, and fresh notice is required if the guaranteed debt is materially altered.
- In the case of *Surakatu v Nigerian Housing Development Ltd*¹⁴, it was held that once the power of sale arises upon default, subsequent payment of arrears does not prevent the sale.
- In the case of *Sabbach v Bank of West Africa Ltd*¹⁵, the court held that although a mortgagee is not a trustee for the mortgagor, he must not act recklessly or fraudulently. If the sale is conducted in good faith, the court will not interfere even if it is disadvantageous to the mortgagor.

Discharge of Mortgage: Upon full repayment of the loan, the mortgagee's interest in the property is extinguished. The mortgagee must return the title deeds and execute a deed of release. Until then, the mortgagee holds the deeds as trustee for safekeeping. In the case of *Bank of the North Ltd v Adehi*¹⁶ - a bank cannot claim alien over property for which it gave no consideration. In the case of *Clark v Woor*¹⁷ - held to be inapplicable as a guide in recovery of land cases. And also in the case of *Estate of Abacha v Eke-Spiff*¹⁸ – reaffirmed principles governing recovery of land.

(ii) **Guarantee**

A guarantee is one of the common mechanisms banks use to safeguard themselves against potential losses on loans and credit facilities. The individual who makes the promise is called the guarantor or surety, the person whose debt is being guaranteed is the principal debtor, and the bank acts as the creditor. To be valid, the guarantor must have the legal capacity to contract, meaning they cannot be a minor or bankrupt. For a bank to enforce a guarantee, it must also fulfill its own contractual obligations. A guarantee is a written commitment by a guarantor to take responsibility for the debt, default, or obligation of another person (the principal debtor), who is primarily liable.

¹²*ACB v Nnaji (1962) All NLR 269*

¹³*Ojikutu v Agbonmagbe Bank Ltd (1966) 1 All NLR*

¹⁴*Surakatu v Nigerian Housing Development Ltd (1981)*

¹⁵*Sabbach v Bank of West Africa Ltd (1962)*

¹⁶*Bank of the North Ltd v Adehi (2003) FWLR (P. 137) 1135 (CA)*

¹⁷*Clark v Woor (1965) 2 All ER 353*

¹⁸*Estate of Abacha v Eke-Spiff (2003) FWLR (Pt. 144) 531 (CA)*

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In the case of *Apugo & Sons Ltd v ACB*¹⁹: The court held that a guarantee is a collateral promise to answer for the debt or default of another, and not an original or direct contract for the promisor's own obligation. Similarly, in the case of *Dikev Kay-Kay Construction Ltd*²⁰: The court held that a guarantee is a secondary agreement, under which the guarantor becomes liable only if the principal debtor defaults. The court further emphasized that by section 4 of the Statute of Frauds 11677, a guarantee must be evidenced in writing and supported by independent consideration. In the same case, the court explained that a guarantor's liability does not arise until the principal debtor defaults. Where the words “**payment guaranteed**” are used, the guarantor becomes liable immediately upon non-payment, without the need to pursue the debtor first, whereas “**collection guaranteed**” requires the creditor to first exhaust remedies against the debtor.

Basis of Guarantee: For a contract of guarantee to exist, there must be a principal debtor who is legally liable. If no valid claim arises against the principal debtor, then no guarantee exists, as affirmed in *Apugo & Sons Ltd v ACB*²¹. The guarantor's liability is conditional and only arises upon default by the principal debtor. Once default occurs, the guarantor becomes liable even without notice.

In the case of *ACB v. Kembi & Talabi*²²: The court held that a surety's liability arises immediately upon default by the principal debtor, and unless otherwise agreed, notice of default is not required. The guarantor remains liable even if not requested to pay, and where the principal debtor dies after default, his personal representatives are liable. In the case of *Western Nigeria Finance Corporation v. Aladesanmi*²³: The court held that where the principal debtor is a statutory body that goes into liquidation, the guarantor becomes primarily liable.

The features of a contract: Must be in writing. Involves three parties: the creditor, the principal debtor, and the guarantor. Imposes secondary liability on the guarantor, enforceable only upon default by the principal debtor. Gives rise to three subsidiary contracts: Between creditor and debtor, between creditor and guarantor, between guarantor and debtor (and among co-guarantors where applicable) Is made at the request of the principal debtor. Entitles the guarantor, after payment, to assume the creditor's rights and recover the sum from the principal debtor.

(iii) Charges

A charge refers to the allocation of real or personal property to secure the repayment of a debt or obligation, without transferring ownership or possession of that property to the creditor. **Goldface-Irokalibe (p.133)** defines it as such. Charges over real property may be either fixed or floating.

Fixed Charge: A fixed charge is created over specific assets of a company and often takes the form of a mortgage debenture over fixed assets, giving rights similar to those of a mortgage.

Charge over Credit Balance: A borrower or even a third party may pledge a credit balance in favor of the bank as security. This can include balances in fixed deposit accounts, savings accounts, current accounts, or short-term deposits. To establish this, the customer or third party signs the bank's standard memorandum of charge over credit balance, which functions as an indemnity. This authorizes the bank to refuse payments or debits that would reduce the charged sum and to liquidate liabilities by debiting the account. Where title documents exist, they must be surrendered to the bank to avoid disputes. In the case of *Birch v Treasury Solicitor*²⁴: An elderly widow handed over her bank deposit books to close friends before her death. The court held that a valid *donation mortis causa* had been made, entitling them to the account balances.

(iv) Domiciliation of Payment: This is a tripartite arrangement involving the customer, a third party obligated to make payment, and the bank. The customer irrevocably instructs the third party to pay funds directly into his bank account as security for facilities. A common example is salary domiciliation, which continues as long as employment subsists. Another form is contract finance, where payment becomes due only upon performance. Once a certificate of performance is issued, it constitutes a valid debt that the bank may discount in anticipation of payment.

(v) Bills Discounting: This involves the bank advancing funds to a customer against the security of a bill. For the bill to be acceptable, it must be a genuine trading bill, properly accepted, transferable without restriction, of reasonable tenure, and backed by creditworthy parties.

Produce and Goods (Trust Receipt and Hypothecation): In trade finance, banks may take a charge over imported goods as security. Although the customer retains physical possession, the bank has constructive possession, with the customer acting as

¹⁹*Apugo & Sons Ltd v ACB (1989) 1 CLRQ 88*

²⁰*Dikev Kay-Kay Construction Ltd (2017) NWLR (Pt. 1584)*

²¹*Apugo & Sons Ltd v ACB (supra)*

²²*ACB v. Kembi & Talabi (19 74) NCLR 282*

²³*Western Nigeria Finance Corporation v. Aladesanmi (1970) NCLR 335*

²⁴*Birch v Treasury Solicitor (1951) Ch 299*

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trustee. The customer signs a letter of hypothecation and often a trust receipt, acknowledging that the goods are held and sold on behalf of the bank, with proceeds payable to the bank. Shipping and insurance documents are usually taken in the bank's name to allow intervention if trust is breached.

Floating Charge: A floating charge is an equitable charge over the present and future assets of a company. It allows the company to freely deal with its assets until the charge crystallizes, which occurs upon cessation of business, appointment of a receiver, or liquidation. In the case of *Re Yorkshire Woolcombers Association Ltd*²⁵: The court identified the characteristics of a floating charge as one covering a class of assets that changes over time and remains under the company's control until crystallization. Also Farwell J in the case of *Re Yorkshire Woolcombers Association Ltd*²⁶: Explained that a charge overlook debts allowing the company to deal with them freely until intervention is not a specific charge but a floating security. Typical assets subject to floating charges include stock, work in progress, cash, and book debts.

Effect of Floating Charge: Floating charges benefit both banks and companies by allowing business continuity without constant interference. However, they carry the risk of asset depreciation, especially when the company faces financial difficulties.

(vi) Stocks, Shares, Debentures and Banking Security

Banks frequently accept stocks, shares, debentures, government securities, and life insurance policies as forms of security for loans and advances. Shares represent a member's stake in a company and their right to dividends, while debentures are instruments acknowledging a company's debt and charging its assets in favor of the lender. Securities may be secured through legal or equitable mortgages over company or government assets.

Shares as Security: Shares can be either quoted or unquoted, and this distinction affects their suitability as collateral. Quoted shares (listed on the Stock Exchange) are preferred because they are stable, easily marketable, and their value can be determined through daily quotations. Unquoted Shares, typically from private companies, are less desirable due to restrictions on transfer under *section 22(2) CAMA 2020*, rights of pre-emption in Articles of Association, and difficulties in valuation caused by the absence of an organized market.

Stock, Bonds, and Government Securities: Banks may also accept treasury bills, bearer bonds, bonds payable to order, and long-term government bonds (such as Development Loan Stocks). Treasury bills are government guaranteed and stable, bearer bonds transfer by delivery, and bonds payable to order require endorsement and delivery. Long-term bonds are less suitable unless the bank's advance is also long-term or near maturity.

(vii) Life Assurance Policy as Security

A life assurance contract involves the insurer agreeing to pay a sum upon the occurrence of an event related to human life, in exchange for periodic premiums.

- Types of policies include whole life (payable only on death), industrial (small sums, generally unsuitable), pure endowment (payable only if the assured survives a fixed period), term assurance (payable if death occurs within a specified time), and endowment (payable on death or after a fixed term, making it the most acceptable as security due to certainty of payment).

Guides for Accepting Life Policies as Security

Banks must consider several factors:

- The type of policy, which must be assignable and have a definite maturity date.
- Insurable interest, without which the policy is void.
- *Kent v. Bird*²⁷: A person insured the safe arrival of a ship in which he had no interest. The court held the policy was a wagering contract and void for lack of insurable interest. **Per Lord Mansfield:** insurance must not be turned into a wager. The insurer must be registered and reputable. The surrender value should be checked to determine the cash value before maturity. Age must be admitted, as it is a material factor. Restrictive clauses (assignment, occupation, travel, reinstatement) must be reviewed. The beneficiary must be clearly identifiable.
- *Tibbets v. Englebach*²⁸: A policy named "**my children**" as beneficiaries. The court held it was unacceptable as security because future children not party to the assignment were included.
- Policies often exclude liability for suicide, execution, war, etc.

Assignment of Life Policies

- **Equitable Assignment:** Created by depositing the policy with the bank along with a memorandum of deposit, forming an equitable charge.

²⁵*Re Yorkshire Woolcombers Association Ltd (1903)*

²⁶*Re Yorkshire Woolcombers Association Ltd (1903) 2 Ch 284*

²⁷*Kent v. Bird (1977) 2 CR 583*

²⁸*Tibbets v. Englebach (1924) 2 Ch 348*

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- **Legal Assignment:** Executed by deed, duly stamped, with notice to and acknowledgment by the insurer. Ownership and benefits pass to the bank until the loan is repaid.

4. Bankers' Legal Rights over Securities

In banking law, the taking of security for loans granted to customers is accompanied by various legal rights which enable bankers to enforce repayment in the event of default. One of the foremost rights is the right of sale. Where security takes the form of pledged goods or a mortgage with a power of sale, the bank is entitled to sell the secured property and apply the proceeds toward the liquidation of the outstanding debt. This remedy allows the banker to recover funds efficiently, subject to compliance with statutory requirements and proper notice to the borrower. The Conveyance Act 1881 provides that a mortgagee whose mortgage is Created by deed has a power of sale when the mortgage money becomes due.

Closely related to this is the right of foreclosure, which arises mainly in mortgage transactions. Foreclosure is the assumption of ownership thereby cancelling the mortgagor's right of redemption of the mortgaged property. The power to foreclose is not automatic as the mortgagee must take a court action to effect it. Through foreclosure proceedings, the borrower's equitable right to redeem the mortgaged property is permanently extinguished, and ownership of the property becomes vested in the bank. This remedy is often employed where sale may be insufficient or impracticable.

Another significant right is the banker's lien. This entitles the bank to retain possession of a customer's goods, securities, or valuables in its custody as security for any outstanding balance owed by the customer. The lien operates automatically in ordinary banking transactions unless expressly excluded by agreement. It was established in *Branado v. Barnett*²⁹ that the general lien of bankers is part of the law merchant and attaches to all securities deposited by a customer, provided they come into the bank's hands in capacity of a banker and in the ordinary course of business. Judicial authorities have affirmed that a banker's lien is equivalent to an implied pledge, allowing the bank to sell securities (*such as Fixed Deposit Receipts*) in its possession if the customer defaults.

The banker also enjoys the right of set-off, which permits the combination of a customer's accounts and the application of credit balances in one account toward the settlement of debts in another. This provides a swift and practical means of recovery without recourse to legal proceedings.

In situations involving charges, particularly floating charges over business assets, the bank may appoint a receiver to take control of the secured property, manage it, and apply the income generated toward repayment of the loan. Notwithstanding the existence of security, the banker retains the right to sue the borrower personally for the debt, as the personal obligation to repay remains intact.

5. Judicial Enforcement of Securities in the Banking Practice

The mere creation of security in banking practice does not automatically guarantee recovery upon default. The effectiveness of security as a risk-mitigation device ultimately depends on the legal and institutional mechanisms available for its enforcement. Judicial and quasi-judicial authorities play a central role in translating the proprietary rights conferred by security interests into actual monetary recovery for banks. In Nigeria, the enforcement of securities operates within a multi-layered legal framework involving regular courts, specialized corporate and insolvency regimes, and appellate courts.

The Role of the Regular Courts

Historically, the enforcement of securities in Nigeria has been primarily the responsibility of the regular courts, particularly the High Courts of the States and the Federal High Court, depending on the subject matter and parties involved. Banks typically approach the courts to enforce mortgages over land, realize charged assets, or obtain orders for foreclosure, possession, and sale. The courts adjudicate disputes arising from the validity of security agreements, compliance with statutory formalities, and allegations of fraud or misrepresentation. Judicial intervention ensures that the enforcement process complies with due process and principles of fairness, thereby protecting both creditor and debtor interests. Nigerian courts have played a crucial role in defining the legal parameters of security enforcement, as seen in landmark decisions such as *Savannah Bank v. Ajilo*³⁰, which underscored the necessity of statutory compliance in mortgage transactions, and *Awojugbagbe Light Industries Ltd v. Chinukwe*³¹, which clarified the legal effect of non-compliance with the Land Use Act. However, while the regular courts provide a robust forum for the vindication of rights, their effectiveness is often hampered by procedural delays, congested dockets, and the technical complexity of banking disputes.

(i) The Role of the Federal High Court in Banking and Commercial Disputes

The Federal High Court occupies a special position in the enforcement of securities in banking practice, particularly in matters involving banks and other financial institutions. By virtue of its jurisdiction over banking, fiscal, and company-related matters, the

²⁹*Branado v. Barnett (1846) 12 CI.*

³⁰*Savannah Bank v. Ajilo (1989)*

³¹*Awojugbagbe Light Industries Ltd v. Chinukwe (1995) 4 NWLR (Pt. 390).*

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Federal High Court often serves as the primary forum for disputes relating to loan recovery and the enforcement of security interests. Its specialized jurisdiction enables it to develop a degree of expertise in complex financial transactions, thereby enhancing the quality and consistency of judicial decisions in banking law. The centralization of certain categories of banking disputes within the Federal High Court also contributes to the development of coherent jurisprudence on security enforcement.

Additionally, the court upheld affirmatory in some of the major cases arising from loan defaults and security enforcements in Nigeria.

*Ekaete v. UBN Plc*³², the Court of Appeal affirmed the nature of debt as a fixed, liquidated sum and upheld the bank's right to enforce recovery. Recognized definition of "debt" and enforceability of bank loan obligations.

*Okafor v. UBN Plc*³³, the bank exercised its right of lien over the customer's account. The court upheld a bank's right to retain funds to recover indebtedness.

*Intercontinental Bank Plc v. Brifina Ltd*³⁴; court upheld the right of a bank to set off funds in a customer's account to settle outstanding debts.

*Awojugbagbe Light Industries v. Chinukwe*³⁵; confirmed the enforceability of equitable mortgages, especially through deposit of title deeds.

*Owoeye v. Bank of Commerce & Industry*³⁶; reinforced a lender's right to sell mortgaged property as long as statutory notices were properly issued.

*Bank of the North v. Bello*³⁷; held that a guarantor is jointly and severally liable once the borrower defaults.

*Diamond Bank Ltd v. Partnership Inv. Co.*³⁸; addressed enforcement of debentures and floating charges against corporate borrowers.

*Skye Bank v. Akinpelu*³⁹; the Supreme Court upheld a bank's right to sue for debt recovery independent of the security, showing that security is a last resort but not a mandatory step before litigation.

(ii) Appellate Courts: The Court of Appeal and the Supreme Court

The Court of Appeal and the Supreme Court play a pivotal supervisory and interpretative role in the enforcement of securities. Through their appellate jurisdiction, these courts resolve conflicting interpretations of banking statutes, clarify the legal status of security interests, and pronounce on the constitutional dimensions of enforcement procedures. The Supreme Court, as the apex court, has been instrumental shaping Nigerian banking law through authoritative pronouncements on the validity of mortgages, the effect of statutory non-compliance, and the rights of secured creditors. Decisions such as *Union Bank of Nigeria Plc v. Ozigi and Savannah Bank v. Ajilo*⁴⁰, exemplify the role of the appellate courts in setting binding precedents that guide lower courts and commercial actors. By providing finality and legal certainty, the appellate courts enhance confidence in the enforcement regime for securities. *Nestoil, Necorde v. FBN (2026) SCN*⁴¹, held by the Supreme Court of Nigeria recently that, receivership cannot assume responsibility to appoint legal representation for defendant in realization of security or assets.

(iii) Quasi-Judicial and Regulatory Oversight

Beyond the traditional court system, regulatory and quasi-judicial bodies influence the enforcement of securities in banking practice. The Central Bank of Nigeria, through its supervisory and regulatory functions under *BOFIA 2020*, indirectly shapes the enforcement landscape by setting prudential standards for credit risk management and provisioning for non-performing loans. While the CBN does not adjudicate disputes between banks and borrowers, its regulatory interventions can affect how banks structure security arrangements and pursue recovery. Additionally, alternative dispute resolution mechanisms, such as arbitration and mediation, are increasingly utilized in banking transactions to resolve disputes arising from security agreements. These quasi-judicial avenues offer the potential for faster and less adversarial resolution, although their outcomes ultimately remain subject to judicial enforcement where coercive measures are required.

³²*Ekaete v. UBN Plc (2014) LPELR-23(CA).*

³³*Okafor v. UBN Plc (2001) 13 NWLR (Pt. 731) 377.*

³⁴*Intercontinental Bank Plc v. Brifina Ltd (2012) 13 NWLR (Pt. 1316) 1.*

³⁵*Awojugbagbe Light Industries v. Chinukwe (1995) 4 NWLR (Pt. 390) 379.*

³⁶*Owoeye v. Bank of Commerce & Industry (1992) 1 NWLR (Pt. 219) 88.*

³⁷*Bank of the North v. Bello (2000) 7 NWLR (Pt. 664) 244.*

³⁸*Diamond Bank Ltd v. Partnership Inv. Co. (2009) 8 NWLR (Pt. 1172) 67.*

³⁹*Skye Bank v. Akinpelu (2010) 9 NWLR (Pt. 1198) 179.*

⁴⁰*Union Bank of Nigeria Plc v. Ozigi (1994) 1 NWLR and Savannah Bank v. Ajilo (supra).*

⁴¹*Nestoil, Necorde v. FBN (2026) SCN.*

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Critical Appraisal of the Enforcement Architecture

The multiplicity of judicial and quasi-judicial authorities involved in the enforcement of securities reflects an attempt to balance efficiency with fairness and legal certainty. On the one hand, judicial oversight ensures that enforcement is conducted in accordance with due process and statutory requirements, thereby protecting borrowers from arbitrary deprivation of property. On the other hand, the reliance on court-based enforcement mechanisms has often resulted in significant delays, which undermine the effectiveness of securities as a last-resort recovery tool. Protracted litigation, interlocutory applications, and appeals can erode the value of secured assets and diminish recovery outcomes. Furthermore, inconsistencies in judicial interpretation across different courts can create uncertainty for banks and borrowers alike. These challenges underscore the need for continued institutional reform and capacity building within the judiciary to enhance the timeliness and predictability of security enforcement.

Judicial precedents have consistently affirmed the role of security as a risk-mitigation tool. In *Union Bank. Tropic Foods Ltd*⁴², the court held that a bank may realize its security upon default, irrespective of concurrent negotiations. *Afribank V. Alade*⁴³ reinforced that a validly created mortgage confers on the bank the right to foreclose and sell the property.

*Diamond Bank v. Partnership Investment Co. Ltd*⁴⁴ clarified that banks must observe due process, including proper notice, before foreclosure, *Intercontinental Bank v. Hilary*⁴⁵ established that courts will not protect defaulting borrowers where security was lawfully obtained. *UBA v. Tejumola & Sons Ltd*⁴⁶ emphasized strict compliance with CAMA registration requirements; non-compliance renders, security void against liquidators.

*Savannah Bank v. Ajilo*⁴⁷ highlighted enforcement difficulties under the Land Use Act, particularly gubernatorial consent requirements that frequently delay or impede recovery. In *CBN v. Inter stella Communications Ltd*⁴⁸, the Supreme Court affirmed the right of banks to realize collateral, contingent upon due process and fairness. Additionally, the Central Bank of Nigeria prescribes regulatory guidelines on loan loss provisioning.

Notwithstanding, this framework, some bankers contend that the characterization of security as a last resort, without contextual qualification, maybe misleading. In their view, security as a final recourse does not imply that it is the sole or optimal means of debt recovery. Rather, it signifies that enforcement should occur only after all other options have been exhausted.

Corporate and Insolvency Adjudication under CAMA 2020

The enforcement of securities in corporate contexts is closely intertwined within solvency and winding-up proceedings under the *Companies and Allied Matters Act 2020*⁴⁹. Where a corporate borrower becomes insolvent, secured creditors may seek to enforce their security either outside the winding-up process or within the collective in solvency framework. The courts, exercising jurisdiction under CAMA, supervise the appointment of receivers and managers, determine the validity and priority of charges, and oversee the distribution of assets. Fixed and floating charges created by companies are subject to registration requirements, and failure to comply with these requirements can affect their enforceability against liquidators and other creditors. Judicial oversight in corporate insolvency ensures that the enforcement of securities aligns with the broader objectives of insolvency law, including the equitable treatment of creditors and the orderly realization of assets.

6. The Doctrine of Last Resort in Loan Recovery

In simple terms, the "last resort" doctrine means that a lender especially a bank should only move to seize collateral or enforce security after genuinely trying every reasonable alternative to help the borrower repay. It reflects equity's long standing dislike for harsh or premature actions that could destroy a debtor's business or livelihood when a workable solution still exists.

*Under the CBN Prudential Guidelines*⁵⁰, once a loan becomes non-performing (i.e., unpaid for 90 days), banks are expected to follow a graduated, humane recovery process:

Stage 1 Demand Notice (30 days): The borrower is formally reminded and given an opportunity to cure the default.

Stage 2 - Restructuring: The bank may extend tenure, reduce instalments, grant a moratorium, or otherwise adjust terms to make repayment feasible.

Stage 3 External Mediation: Neutral third parties help both sides reach a workable settlement.

Stage 4 Enforcement: Only when all prior efforts fail should the bank enforce security (e.g., foreclosure, receivership, asset sale).

⁴²*Union Bank. Tropic Foods Ltd (1992).*

⁴³*Afribank V. Alade (2000).*

⁴⁴*Diamond Bank v. Partnership Investment Co. Ltd (2009).*

⁴⁵*Intercontinental Bank v. Hilary (2010).*

⁴⁶*UBA v. Tejumola & Sons Ltd (1988).*

⁴⁷*Savannah Bank v. Ajilo' (1989).*

⁴⁸*CBN v. Inter stella Communications Ltd (2018).*

⁴⁹*Companies and Allied Matters Act 2020.*

⁵⁰*Under the CBN Prudential Guidelines (2024).*

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This layered approach also reflected in **BOFIA** - exists to prevent rash enforcement actions that could unnecessarily push borrowers into insolvency, destroy viable businesses, or trigger wider economic instability.

The courts have reinforced this philosophy. In *FBN Plc v. Maiwada*⁵¹, the Court of Appeal held that foreclosure carried out without evidence of genuine negotiation attempts was oppressive and therefore invalid. The decision underscores that enforcement powers must be exercised responsibly, not mechanically.

Comparable safeguards exist internationally. *India's SARFAESI Act*⁵² requires statutory notice periods before enforcement, emphasizing that borrowers must be given a fair chance to regularize their accounts. The idea is the same: enforcement is not meant to be the first reaction, but the final option.

From a policy perspective, the doctrine promotes forbearance rather than punishment. It recognizes that many defaults arise from temporary distress economic downturns, cash-flow issues, or unexpected shocks -rather than bad faith. Supporting recovery instead of liquidation preserves jobs, protects assets value, and stabilizes the financial system.

Empirical data supports this approach. NDIC figures indicating that about 70% of non-performing loans in 2025 were resolved through restructuring show that cooperative solutions often succeed where aggressive enforcement might destroy value for both parties.

Ultimately, the "last resort" doctrine balances two important interests:

- The lender's right to recover its money
- The borrower's right to fair treatment and economic survival

By insisting that enforcement comes only after sincere efforts at resolution, the law encourages responsible banking, reduces systemic risk, and aligns financial practice with principles of fairness and commercial common sense.

Security is the banker's last resort because the bank does not primarily recover loan from security. The bank primarily expects repayment from the borrower's business income, cash flow and other financial means, not directly from the security. Security enforcement such foreclosure and sale of collateral is typically the last resort. Before the bank resort to enforcing security. the bank takes certain steps including first demanding for repayment. Once the agreed time is up, the bank sends demand letters to the borrower, which includes the outstanding amount, and the intention to recover the loan from the security. Also, the bank could re-negotiate with the customer and help extend the time for repayment. The bank could also restructure the loan and allow the borrower to pay in instalment. This shows the banks reliance on the customer's cash flow rather than the security.

The bank could also set off or appropriate the payment, although it is subject to the customers' approval unless the contract. signed by the customer specifies otherwise. The bank prefers other means to recover the payment, and only resort to security as the last means because the realization of security is expensive and time consuming. Also, it involves statutory regulations and court orders. Example is the regulations as regards to mortgage stated in *S.21 and S.22 of the Land Use Act 1978*⁵³. Another reason is that the value of security changes and sometimes depreciate. For example, the value of land does not remain the same. It changes

The bank makes use of security because their priority is recovering the loan. Also, the bank resort to security upon default of customer. The bank will not use security if the customer did not default. Security does not replace debt as the bank could still sue the de faulting customer where the security is not enough to cover the amount, the balance. In *Union Bank of Nigeria Ltd v. Ozigi*⁵⁴, the supreme court held that a banks does not lend money on the security alone but on the faith of the borrower's ability to repay. the security is just the fall back.

7. Appraisal of the Significance and Challenges of Security as Last Resort

Preservation of Business Relationships: By treating security as a last resort, lenders can preserve their business relationships with borrowers. This approach allows lenders to work with borrowers to restructure loans or provide additional support, rather than immediately enforcing their security.

Avoidance of Unnecessary Costs: Enforcing security can be a costly and time-consuming process. By treating security as a last resort, lenders can avoid unnecessary costs and minimize their losses.

Promoting Borrower Responsibility: By giving borrowers a second chance to rectify their default, lenders can promote borrower responsibility and encourage borrowers to take their obligations more seriously.

It also, enhances the likelihood of loan recovery, by having recourse to valuable assets upon default, banks are able to realize outstanding debts through enforcement mechanisms such as sale or foreclosure. This significantly reduces the risk of complete financial loss. Security also serves to minimize credit risk by ensuring that loans are backed by tangible assets or

⁵¹*FBN Plc v. Maiwada (2013) 32 E-WRN/31 (SC).*

⁵²*India's SARFAESI Act 2002.*

⁵³*S.21 and S.22 of the Land Use Act 1978.*

⁵⁴*Union Bank of Nigeria Ltd v. Ozigi 1994 (SUPRA).*

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enforceable rights, thereby encouraging prudent lending practices. Another important benefit of security is that it promotes financial discipline among borrowers. The prospect of losing valuable property motivates customers to fulfill their repayment obligations and discourages reckless borrowing. Furthermore, by reducing bad debts and non-performing loans, security strengthens the financial position of banks and contributes to the overall stability of the banking system, which in turn fosters public confidence.

Despite these lofty advantages, security is not without limitations. One major challenge is the depreciation of secured assets, particularly movable property such as vehicles and machinery, which may lose value over time and become insufficient to cover the outstanding loan. In addition, the enforcement of security often involves legal procedures that can be time-consuming and costly, thereby delaying recovery. Another limitation arises from fraudulent or defective titles. Where borrowers offer property with improper documentation or unclear ownership, banks may face difficulties in enforcing their security interests. Market fluctuations may also reduce the value of secured assets, especially in times of economic instability. Moreover, practical difficulties in seizing, managing, and selling certain assets may further hinder effective recovery.

Finally, whilst security provides an essential safeguard for banks and greatly enhances loan recovery, its effectiveness is sometimes undermined by legal, economic and political challenges. Nevertheless, it remains a vital instrument in banking law and practice.

8. Concluding Remarks and Recommendations

Security play a fundamental role in the law of banking as a protective mechanism through which banks safeguard loans granted to customers. Although the primary expectation of repayment lies in the borrowers' income or business proceed, security serves as a vital secondary source of recovery and becomes the banks last resort where default occurs, through various forms of personal and proprietary securities, banks are able to reduce credit risk and enforce legal rights over secured assets.

In the final analysis, security occupy a central and indispensable position within banking law as the ultimate legal recourse available to financial institutions in the event of loan default. They perform a critical risk mitigation function by transforming what would otherwise be a purely personal claim for repayment with a proprietary right over identifiable assets. The proprietary character elevates the bank from the status of an unsecured creditor to that of a secured creditor with priority claims, thereby enhancing the safety of depositor's funds, promoting confidence in the credit system and contributing to the overall stability of the financial sector.

However, the effectiveness of securities as the last line of defense is not automatic, it's fundamentally conditioned by the presence of the essential legal elements required for validity and enforceability. A security must be anchored on valid principal obligation, created with clear intentions supported by the legal capacity and title attached to identifiable and transferable collateral perfected in the strict compliance with statutory formalities and proper documentation. The occurrence of default and the absence of vitiating factors such as fraud and illegality further determine whether a security can be successfully enforced in practice. Non-compliance with any of these requirements exposes the bank's security to legal vulnerability and may defeat its intended protective function. The law further strengthens the effectiveness of security by granting banks several enforcement rights, including sales, foreclosure, lien, set-off and the appointment of receivers. These rights enable banks to recover outstanding debts and maintain stability. However, the practical operation of security is not without challenges such as depreciation of assets, legal delays, fraudulent title and market uncertainties.

Conclusively, whilst security does not entirely eliminate the risks associated with lending, it significantly enhances the ability of banks to recover defaulted loans and continues to play a crucial role as the final last resort in banking loan transactions.

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